

Reaction of rice varieties in the 1984 International Rice Whitebacked Planthopper Nursery (IRWBPHN)

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We screened rice varieties entered in the 1984 IRWBPHN 1984 for resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* H. in the IRRI greenhouse (see table).

Seeds of 85 entries were sown 9 Oct in 60- × 40- × 10- cm wooden seedboxes filled with fertile soil. The experiment was in a completely randomized block design with three replications. One row of 25 seeds/variety was 1 replication. Susceptible TN1 and resistant IR2035-117-3 were checks. Seven-day-old seedlings were each infested with about 5 2d- and 3d-instar WBPH nymphs. Damage was rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 8 d after infestation (DI) when TN1 was hopperburned, and 10 DI when most varieties were hopperburned.

At 8 DI, 55%, of all entries were resistant. At 10 DI, only 18% were

resistant. Of the varieties tested, IR2035-117-3 has *Wbph 1* and *Wbph 2* genes for resistance. It, however, rated only moderately resistant. Several of its

progeny were resistant. IR17307-11-2-3-2 was also resistant. It has IR2070-423 and N22 (with *Wbph 1*) as parents. *ℳ*

Screening wild rices for resistance to *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley

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We screened 227 wild rices for resistance to rice leafhopper *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley using the screening method developed for *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée.

In the first test, entries were sown in seedboxes; 15 d after sowing (DAS), the plants were transplanted in 12-cm-diameter pots at 5 plants/pot. Test entries and one pot of susceptible TN1 (*Oryza sativa*) and resistant TKM6 (*O. sativa*) were covered with a fiberglass screen cage. Ten pair of adults were released in each cage and allowed to oviposit on the plants. Twenty-one days later, the pots were removed from the

tray and damage on each leaf was determined based on the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. The experiment was in six replications,

Entries that scored 0-3 were retested in 6 replications, with each pot representing 1 replication. Treatments were in a randomized complete block design. At 21 DAS, plants were infested with 2 1st-instar larvae/tiller. Damage was recorded 17 d later.

Of the 227 wild rices, 19 were resistant, 48 were moderately resistant, and 160 were susceptible (see table).

Accessions 101232 and 101236 that were highly resistant to *C. medinalis* were also resistant to *M. patnalis*. The *O. brachyantha* accessions from West Africa were more resistant to *M. patnalis* than any *O. sativa* accessions that we have screened. *ℳ*

Wild rices resistant to *Marasmia patnalis*. IRRI.

Species	Origin	IRRI accession no.	Damage rating ^a
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Thailand	100192	3
<i>O. stapfii</i>	Nigeria	100936	3
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	India	102177	3
<i>Oryza</i> sp.	Bangladesh	102471	3
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Burma	100926	3
<i>O. barthii</i>	Guinea-Conakry	100929	3
<i>O. sativa/O. rufipogon</i>	Nigeria	100938	3
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	Sierra Leone	101231	3
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	Sierra Leone	101232	1
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	Sierra Leone	101235	1
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	Mali Republic	101236	1
<i>O. barthii</i>	Mali Republic	101940	3
<i>O. barthii</i>	Mali Republic	101941	3
<i>O. brachyantha/O. barthii</i>	Upper Volta	101954	3
<i>O. nivara</i>	Sri Lanka	103419	3
<i>O. nivara/O. sativa</i>	Sri Lanka	103791	3
<i>O. sativa/O. rufipogon</i>	Sri Lanka	103793	3
<i>O. rufipogon/O. nivara</i>	Burma	103799	3
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Bangladesh	103844	3
TKM6 (resistant check)	India	237	3
TN 1 (susceptible check)	Taiwan	105	9

^a By the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

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Entries with WBPH resistance at 10 DI in the 1984 IRWBPHN, IRRI.

Designation	Cross	Origin
ADR52		India
Balamawee		Sri Lanka
Chempan		India
Cheriyachittari		India
CI 5662-2		Japan
IR15527-21-2-3	IR2035-117-3/ IR30//IR2037-64-2-2	IRRI
IR15529-253-3-2-2-2	IR2035-117-3/ IR2061-522-6-9//IR2037-64-2-2	IRRI
IR15795-151-2-3-2-2	IR2035-117-3/ 2*IR36	IRRI
IR15797-74-1-3-2	IR2035-117-3/ IR2153-26-3-5-6//IR2061-465-1-5-5	IRRI
IR17307-11-2-3-2	IR2070-423/N22 //2*IR2070-423-2//IR2070-423-2-5-6	IRRI
Latighawar		Nepal
Sinna Sivappu		Sri Lanka
Sufaida 172		Pakistan
Valsara champara		India
WC1240		India